

Diphenylcarbazide and Diphenylcarbazone. Part II. Polarographic Study on Diphenylcarbazone

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A polarographic study of the system $\text{RH}_2 + 2\text{H}^+ + 2e^- \rightleftharpoons \text{RH}_4$, has been made (RH_2 =diphenylcarbazone and RH_4 =diphenylcarbazide). The reaction appears to be an irreversible one at the dropping mercury cathode. $E_{1/2}$ values found against S.C.E. and mercury pool anode are +0.085V and -0.042V respectively at 32°. The polarographic estimation of diphenylcarbazone at $\text{pH}=0.7$ has been described. The interference due to diphenylcarbazide has also been studied. The polarograms for the coloured solutions, formed by the reaction between chromic acid and diphenylcarbazide in different ratios, indicate the presence of free diphenylcarbazone as one of the reaction products and another reducible compound, presumably to be a complex compound of chromium with diphenylcarbazone.

In our previous communication (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 650), the volumetric estimation of diphenylcarbazide and diphenylcarbazone has been described. The present paper constitutes a study on diphenylcarbazone polarographically. It has been assumed that diphenylcarbazone is reduced at the dropping mercury cathode according to the equation:

where RH_2 =diphenylcarbazone and RH_4 =diphenylcarbazide. It is apparent that $E_{1/2}$ values of the system are dependent on hydrogen-ion concentration. The effect of pH on $E_{1/2}$ values has been studied systematically and the values are found to be fairly constant at pH ranges between 1.3 and 0.6. So the polarographic estimation has been undertaken at these pH ranges.

The reaction (1) appears to be irreversible, as the straight line could not be drawn through all the points by plotting $E_{d.e.}$ versus $\log (i_d - i)/i$. The interference due to diphenylcarbazide in the estimation of diphenylcarbazone has been studied and the results are found to follow an empirical relation:

$$E'_{1/2} = E_{1/2} + 0.03 \log \left(1 + \frac{2\text{RH}_4}{\text{RH}_2} \right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where $E_{1/2}$ =half-wave potential and $E'_{1/2}$ =observed half-wave potential. The $E'_{1/2}$ values are found to be shifted towards less negative, which may be due to slower reaction rates of this conjugate oxidant-reductant pair.

Polarograms, obtained for the coloured solutions formed by the reaction between chromic acid and diphenylcarbazide in different ratios, indicate the presence of free diphenylcarbazone as one of the reaction products and another reducible compound, which is pro-

bably the complex compound of chromium with diphenylcarbazone. As it has already been shown by Job's method of continued variation (Bose, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 10, 209; Pflaum and Howick, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 4862) that maximum coloration takes place while reacting at the ratio of two moles of chromic acid to three moles of diphenylcarbazide, the reaction may therefore be represented in the following way:

Further investigations are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Polarographic measurements were carried out on a Cambridge pen recording polarograph and against the mercury pool anode except otherwise mentioned. The electrode employed has a drop time of 3.15 sec. and a mass-drop time ($m^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\frac{1}{3}}$) value of 1.59 (in water at zero-volt applied potential).

Diphenylcarbazone was purified by recrystallisation from ether. Glacial acetic was distilled over chromic acid. Other reagents employed were of A.R. quality.

A known amount of diphenylcarbazone (appr. 0.012 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (12.5 c.c.) and diluted to 50 c.c. with water; an aliquot was used for polarographic study. The solutions electrolysed were composed of known volumes of diphenylcarbazone solution, (the supporting electrolyte potassium nitrate), and water to dilute to a required volume; pH of the solutions was varied from 4.98 to 0.56 by adding either dilute sulphuric acid or sodium hydroxide solution, whichever was necessary. The solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling hydrogen for 15 minutes and polarograms were obtained over the range 0.05V to-0.15V. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Diphenylcarbazone (0.0244 g.) was dissolved in 25 c.c. of acetic acid and diluted with water to 100 c.c. An aliquot of 5 c.c. was taken for each subsequent solution. The final volume was made to 25 c.c. with water. Sensitivity=1/5. Damping=3.

2M-KNO ₃ .	1.64N-KOH.	1N-H ₂ SO ₄ .	3.63N-AcOH.	pH.	E ₁ .
6.1 c.c.	7.70 c.c.	..	..	4.98	-0.054 volts
8.8	4.40	..	..	4.48	-0.048
10.7	2.20	..	..	4.04	-0.046
11.2	1.65	..	..	3.82	-0.045
12.0	0.55	..	..	3.31	-0.045
12.3	0.20	..	..	2.75	-0.044
12.5	..	..	..	2.17	-0.044
12.5	..	..	5.0	2.08	-0.044
12.5	..	0.50 c.c.	..	1.65	-0.043
12.5	..	1.00	..	1.32	-0.042
12.5	..	2.50	..	0.98	-0.042
12.5	..	5.00	..	0.70	-0.042
12.5	..	7.00	..	0.56	-0.042

Typical polarograms are shown in Fig. 1. $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values were found to be +0.085V and 0.042V at 32° against S.C.E. and mercury pool anode respectively.

FIG. 1

- (a) Against S.C.E. Sensitivity = 1/15. Damping = 3. $C_{RH_2} = 4.3 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 (b) ,, mercury pool anode. Sensitivity = 1/5. Damping = 3. $C_{RH_2} = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Polarographic estimation of diphenylcarbazone was carried out at pH 0.7. The results obtained are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Diphenylcarbazone (0.0120 g.) was dissolved in 12.5 c.c. of acetic acid and diluted to 50 c.c. with water. Different volumes of this solution, 10 c.c. of 2M-KNO₃ and 5 c.c. of 1N-H₂SO₄ were taken and diluted to 25 c.c. with water. Sensitivity = 1/7. Damping = 3.

RH ₂ solution.	Wave-height found.	Height per c.c.
6 c.c.	30.4	5.07
5	25.5	5.10
4	20.0	5.00

The interference due to diphenylcarbazide was studied. $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values were found to be shifted and consequently diphenylcarbazone could not be estimated polarographically in presence of diphenylcarbazide. The results were, however, found to follow the relation:

$$E'_{\frac{1}{2}} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} + 0.03 \log \left(1 + \frac{2RH_2}{RH_2} \right)$$

The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Diphenylcarbazone (0.0122 g.) was dissolved in 12.5 c.c. of acetic acid and diluted to 50 c.c. with water (solution 'A'). The solution 'B' was of diphenylcarbazide (0.0125 g.) in 12.5 c.c. of acetic acid and the volume was made to 50 c.c. with water. For each subsequent solution 5 c.c. of 'A', 10 c.c. of 2M-KNO₃, 5 c.c. of 1N-H₂SO₄ and, different volumes of 'B' were taken and diluted to 25 c.c. with water.

TABLE III (contd.)

Solution 'B'.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ found.	RH_4/RH_2	
		Found.	Calc.
0.0 c.c.	-0.042 volts		
0.2	-0.041	0.040	0.041
0.6	-0.039	0.130	0.123
1.0	-0.037	0.234	0.203
2.0	-0.034	0.424	0.406
3.0	-0.032	0.577	0.609
5.0	-0.028	0.965	1.016

Polarograms were obtained of the coloured solutions prepared by mixing diphenylcarbazide and chromic acid in different ratios in presence of $0.2N-H_2SO_4$ and $0.8M-KNO_3$. These are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2. Ratio of chromic acid to diphenylcarbazide. (a) 1.10, (b) 0.85, (c) 0.66, (d) 0.60, (e) 0.50.

Examination of the polarographic waves indicates that the first step is due to diphenylcarbazone, $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values appearing to be shifted toward less negative where ratios < 0.67 are evidently due to the presence of unchanged diphenylcarbazide. $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values of the second step are shifted toward more negative, due perhaps to complex-bound diphenylcarbazone.